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Scientific and tourist expedition to Haikou City and surroundings on Hainan Island, south China

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ABSTRACT

This work is to present the documentation of scientific and tourist expedition to Haikou city and surroundings on Hainan Island, south China, which took place in July 2007. The main aim of this expedition was to take part in the *Fifteenth Annual International Conference on Composites/Nano Engineering (ICCE-15)*. The second aim of this expedition was to document the beauty of Haikou city and landscapes of the surrounding area. Haikou city is modern, clean with large skyscrapers, which is constantly developing. Red and yellow are dominating colors in the city. South of the Haikou city is densely overgrown with tropical vegetation, with humid climate. About 15 kilometers south of the Haikou city there is Haikou Volcanic Cluster Global Geopark, as a tourist attraction visited by domestic and foreign tourists.

Keywords: International conference, south China, Haikou city, Hainan Island, geography, tourism, Haikou Volcanic Cluster Global Geopark

INTRODUCTION

The Scientific and tourist expedition started from the capital of Poland, Warsaw, from Okęcie airport by Russian Airlines to Shanghai, China, transit through Moscow, Russia, in July 2007 (**Figs. 1-4**). On the next day, after reaching Shanghai, the weather was ugly, cloudy, it was lightly raining (**Figs. 5 & 6**) [1-10].

The airport in Shanghai was very beautiful, modern and clean (**Figs. 7-10**). After going out of the airport, the air was very humid, it was muggy. There was smell of ubiquitous exhaust fumes. Shanghai city directly influences on the state of air pollution even at the airport.

After a few hours spent at the airport in Shanghai, the Scientific expedition arrived with the Chinese Airlines by night to Haikou city on Hainan Island. The Haikou airport is beautiful, clean and modern (**Fig. 11**).

Hainan is the biggest island of Chinese People's Republic of the surface area of 33,920 km². It is separated by Hainan Straits from Leizhou Peninsula in Guangdong Province. West of the Island there is Gulf of Tonkin. The highest elevation on Hainan Island is Wuzhi Shan (1876 meters above sea level). On this Island, the biggest city is Haikou, with the population of about 2 million. There at the Haikou airport, the expedition was informed that the Hainan Island is comparable to Hawaii Islands (USA), concerning the beauty of landscapes (**Map 1**).

After getting from the Haikou airport by taxi to the hotel by night, it turned out the hotel was a high class concerning culture and service (**Figs. 12-14**). In the morning in Haikou city, a traditional Chinese gymnastic Tai-Chi was observed (**Figs. 15 & 16**).

In **Figures 17-23**, traditional fishing boats located in the channel at low tide are presented. These boats are used not only for catching fish but above all they serve as floating houses on the water. Residents live in them, often the whole families who live off fishing.

One can often meet, characteristic for the tropical climate, bamboos which in China are used as lightweight and durable materials for construction of even very tall buildings (scaffolding), (**Figs. 24 & 25**).

Map 1. Hainan Island, China.
(www.google.com)

Haikou is a very modern city. It has many skyscrapers. There are shops with colorful neon signs and signs in Chinese but it is very rare to see a signboard in English. Dominating colors in the city are red and yellow. In July in the city the temperature is about 40 °C in the shade. Sunny, muggy and humid (tropical) – is the climate standard during this period in the city (**Figs. 26-50**).

Car traffic is ubiquitous, traffic jams at intersections are the same as all over the world in the big city, but with a lot of chaos. Modern cars of Japanese and Korean origin are the main brands of these vehicles. Sometimes one can meet European cars, especially German cars such as Volkswagen, used as a taxi. Traditional vehicles from Southeast Asia, the so-called Tuk-Tuk (tricycles) are discernible, serving as transport vehicles and a taxi.

For the entire period of being in Haikou city and surroundings (Hainan Island), the Scientific expedition was constantly monitored by Chinese secret services. They were hiding though apparent. Japanese and/or Korean origin brand cars with tinted windows (it was

impossible to see who was inside), they were still following the crew. The Scientific crew was not taking photos of this phenomenon for safety reasons.

Hainan Island is a wonderful island, geologically diversified, as displayed in **Figures 51-75**. The photos present Haikou Volcanic Cluster Global Geopark, also known as Haikou Scenic-Shishan Volcano Cluster, Leiqiong Global Geopark, Haikou Crater Park and Hainan Crater Park is a national park located about 8 miles south of Haikou, Hainan, China. Its name comes from the crater, one of the extinct volcanoes on the Island [11-19].

The total area of the park is 118 km². There are two cities on its territory: Shishan Town and Yongxing Town as well as over 40 quaternary volcanoes. The part of this area is called Landscape Area of Maanling Crater Mountain. This area consists of two main volcanoes: Mount Fengliung and Mount Baoziling. Together they form a saddle, hence the name. Next to them are located two more other volcanoes, one of which is named Yanjinglin. Most of the park area along with volcanic craters are densely covered with tropical vegetation.

During the Fifteenth Annual International Conference on Composites/Nano Engineering (ICCE-15), Haikou, Hainan Island, 2007, which was held in days 15-21 of July, 2007, the authors published two papers at this conference in the post-conference materials [20-22]:

1. Tomasz Borowski. Sodium Polybutadiene Battery as the Source of Ecologic Energy. *Fifteenth Annual International Conference on Composites/Nano Engineering (ICCE-15)*, July 15-21, 2007, Haikou, Hainan, China, pp. 100-101
2. Tadeusz Hryniewicz, Ryszard Rokicki. On the Modification of Surface Properties of Stainless Steels. *Fifteenth Annual International Conference on Composites/Nano Engineering (ICCE-15)*, July 15-21, 2007, Haikou, Hainan, China, pp. 345-346

After all lectures were finished with various specialties, on the last day of the conference the organizers arranged a banquet with music, with dinner and dancing (**Figs. 76-90**).

Beaches away from the city of Haikou are heavily contaminated – mainly with plastic wastes. Generally out of the city, the civilization pollution is ubiquitous (**Figs. 91-94**).

At noon the sun shines almost vertically, temperature in the shade was 45 °C (**Fig. 95**).

While in Haikou city on the island of Hainan, the Hainan University was visited. In the period of 2006-2007, the total number of students reached over a dozen of thousands, which makes an impression of very small number in relation to the population all over China. University and Campus are very varied inside, with tennis courts, basketball courts, indoor nature park, library, etc. (**Figs. 96-144**).

In **Figures 145 & 146**, there are displayed chemical reagent and laboratory glassware shop/market in the city center of Haikou.

The next picture shows a traditional Chinese siesta in the city center of Haikou (**Fig. 147**).

Markets on the island of Hainan are very modern and well-equipped, though there are numerous traditional shops, stores and small boutiques (**Figs. 148-151**).

In the inhabited hotel in Haikou city center, there is full comfort: restaurant, swimming pool, internet but controlled, such as e.g. telephone (previously ordered) (**Figs. 152-154**).

The return trip from Hainan Island to Poland took place by Chinese Airlines, first going to Hong Kong (**Figs. 155-159**).

In **Figures 160-179**, there are displayed a modern airport and surroundings in Hong Kong. Temperature in Hong Kong was about 40 °C: muggy, warmth and hot. Return journey to

Warsaw, Poland, took place by Russian Airlines by transit through Moscow, Russia (**Figs. 180-182**) [23-43].

CONCLUSION

The entire scientific and tourist expedition, which took place in July 2007, reflected with a big impression with a new another world and other culture. Beautiful modern city of Haikou as well as all the nature of Hainan Island was noteworthy documenting in the form of photos. The scientific conference: *Fifteenth Annual International Conference on Composites/Nano Engineering (ICCE-15)*, was really professionally run. Guests coming from almost all over the world to the conference were kindly greeted and taken care of throughout this event.

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APPENDIX

Fig. 1. Okęcie airport in Warsaw, Poland.

Fig. 2. Okęcie airport in Warsaw, Poland.

Fig. 3. Okęcie airport in Warsaw, Poland.

Fig. 4. Flight from Moscow to Shanghai.

Fig. 5. Airport in Shanghai, China.

Fig. 6. Airport in Shanghai, China.

Fig. 7. Airport in Shanghai, China.

Fig. 8. Airport in Shanghai, China.

Fig. 9. Airport in Shanghai, China.

Fig. 10. Airport in Shanghai, China.

Fig. 11. Airport in Haikou city on Hainan Island, China.

Fig. 12. Hotel in Haikou city.

Fig. 13. Hotel in Haikou city.

Fig. 14. Hotel in Haikou city.

Fig. 15. Morning traditional Chinese gymnastics Tai-Chi in Haikou city.

Fig. 16. Morning traditional Chinese gymnastics Tai-Chi in Haikou city.

Fig. 17. Fishing boats used as homes//apartments.

Fig. 18. Fishing boats used as homes//apartments.

Fig. 19. Fishing boats used as homes//apartments.

Fig. 20. Fishing boats used as homes//apartments.

Fig. 21. Fishing boats used as homes//apartments.

Fig. 22. Fishing boats used as homes//apartments.

Fig. 23. Fishing boats used as homes//apartments.

Fig. 24. Bamboos growing in the park in Haikou city.

Fig. 25. The use of bamboo as a building//construction material – scaffolding.

Fig. 26. Modern city view of Haikou.

Fig. 27. Modern city view of Haikou.

Fig. 28. Modern city view of Haikou.

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Fig. 50. Modern city view of Haikou.

Fig. 51. Shishan Volcanic Cluster National Geopark of Haikou.

Fig. 52. Shishan Volcanic Cluster National Geopark of Haikou.

Fig. 53. Shishan Volcanic Cluster National Geopark of Haikou.

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Fig. 76. Photos of Fifteenth Annual International Conference on Composites/Nano Engineering (ICCE-15), Haikou, Hainan Island, 2007.

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Fig. 89. Photos of Fifteenth Annual International Conference on Composites/Nano Engineering (ICCE-15), Haikou, Hainan Island, 2007.

Fig. 90. Photos of Fifteenth Annual International Conference on Composites/Nano Engineering (ICCE-15), Haikou, Hainan Island, 2007.

Fig. 91. Beach near the city of Haikou.

Fig. 92. Beach near the city of Haikou.

Fig. 93. Beach near the city of Haikou.

Fig. 94. Beach near the city of Haikou (Author and initiator of the expedition: T. Borowski).

Fig. 95. At noon, the sun shines almost vertically.

Fig. 96. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 97. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 98. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 99. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

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(Author and initiator of the expedition: T. Borowski).

Fig. 109. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

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Fig. 121. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

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(Author and initiator of the expedition: T. Borowski).

Fig. 123. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

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Fig. 125. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan
(Author and initiator of the expedition: T. Borowski).

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Fig. 128. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 129. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 130. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 131. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 132. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan (Author and initiator of the expedition: T. Borowski).

Fig. 133. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 134. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 135. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 136. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 137. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 138. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 139. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 140. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 141. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 142. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan
(Author and initiator of the expedition: T. Borowski).

Fig. 143. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan
(Author and initiator of the expedition: T. Borowski) .

Fig. 144. Area of the University and Campus in Hainan.

Fig. 145. Market with chemical reagents and laboratory glassware in the city centre of Haikou.

Fig. 146. Market with chemical reagents and laboratory glassware in the city centre of Haikou.

Fig. 147. A look on the noon siesta on Hainan Island.

Fig. 148. Modern and richly equipped markets on Hainan Island, with some traditional shops and boutiques around.

Fig. 149. Modern and richly equipped markets on Hainan Island, with some traditional shops and boutiques around.

Fig. 150. Modern and richly equipped markets on Hainan Island, with some traditional shops and boutiques around.

Fig. 151. Modern and richly equipped markets on Hainan Island, with some traditional shops and boutiques around.

Fig. 152. Facilities//Attractions in the hotel: restaurant, swimming pool, internet, etc.

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Fig. 155. Air cruise from the airport on Hainan Island by Chinese Airlines to Hong Kong.
(Author and initiator of the expedition: T. Borowski).

Fig. 156. Air cruise from the airport on Hainan Island by Chinese Airlines to Hong Kong
(Author and initiator of the expedition: T. Borowski).

Fig. 157. Air cruise from the airport on Hainan Island by Chinese Airlines to Hong Kong.

Fig. 158. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

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Fig. 161. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

Fig. 162. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

Fig. 163. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

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Fig. 167. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

Fig. 168. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

Fig. 169. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

Fig. 170. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

Fig. 171. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

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Fig. 176. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

Fig. 177. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

Fig. 178. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

Fig. 179. Hong Kong – modern airport and surroundings.

Fig. 180. Flight from Hong Kong to Warsaw (Russian Airlines).

Fig. 181. Flight from Hong Kong to Warsaw (Russian Airlines).

Fig. 182. Flight from Hong Kong to Warsaw (Russian Airlines).